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GREEN COMPUTING

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ABSTRACT:

Green computing is based on the study of computing resources. Green computing was introduced shortly after introducing the energy star program. Green computing is been also know as green technology. In the year 1992, energy star program was launched by US environmental protection agency. Energy star program was designed for the purpose to promote and recognize energy efficiency in some technologies. Energy management is been more useful for the laptop manufactures in the process of battery life and less weight. When green computing is been used there will be less usage of energy. And it has been used for the disposal of the products which is been taken into the recycling process. The main reason for using green is to save energy and to save the money. Now-a-days green computing process are followed by the business people for the office use. Government also approved some policy to encourage the green computing and the recycling process. Triple bottom line was the objective of the green computing but the companies focused only the bottom line not the triple bottom line.

Keywords: *green computing, energy management, recycling, money management.*

INTRODUCTION:

Green computing is based on the study of computing resources. Green computing has some primary objective program which is to account for the triple bottom line. The term green was introduced few years later when the scientist found that our environment was renewable resources. To protect our environment people took some effort and the term green was brought in. The main aim behind the energy efficiency is to save energy and the hardware to be used less. When the green computing was introduced all we thought is "GOING GREEN WITH THE COMPUTERS" and

the question raised was “HOW” and what will be the reason to implement green computing. The green computing has the capacity to invent and manage to the industry standards of “EFGCD”. EFGCD means eco friendly green computing definitions. EFGCD is defined as the study and practise of the design, development, implementation, utilization and disposal of IT infrastructure efficiently and effectively with low or zero impact on the environment while reducing operating costs.

Approaches to Virtualization:

Virtualization is a process of running two or more logical computer system on one set of physical hardware. This concept was brought in with the help of the IBM mainframe operating system in the year 1960's but it was used only for the compatible computers in the year 1990's. Virtualization was helping the organizations to consolidate their server into a small pieces of hardware and which is resulted to the sizeable cost saving. In the idea of green computing, virtualization plays a good role by consolidating servers and maximizing CPU processing power on the other servers. Virtualization storage is used to reduce the number of storage device by accessing a shared storage subsystem that is somewhere out on the net. It is meant that the copies of the data to be stored in the every computer disk can be stored once in the shared storage subsystem.

A) Power management:

Computer system use power management for some reasons and the reason are listed below:

- Portable systems need a long battery life.
- Reduction on cooling requirements and operating cost for energy.
- System ability is increased by less power consumption and the cost is saved by the use of less energy.
- The power saving is directly controlled by the advanced configuration and power interface which allows an operating system to turn off the components automatically like monitor and hard drives.
- The voltage supplied to the CPU is manually adjusted by the user to reduce the amount of heat produced and electricity consumed.
- The above process is termed as “**undervaluing**”.

In the microprocessor, power management can be done over the whole process or in a specific area.

B) power supply:

In the most computers, power supplies are not developed for the energy efficiency.

C)Storage:

It provides three ways which all are depending on the cost, performance and capacity. The advantage of this way is the best performance and highest possible capacity. Power consumption is been increased when there is increase in the online storage.

D) Video card:

In the computer the largest power consumer is GPU.

Energy efficiency display option includes some features which are listed below:

- For the low 3D performance and low power motherboard video display is been used.

- The video card which uses the less power is been reused where some of the video card do not require heat sinks or fans.
- The GPU is been selected based on the average wattage or performance per watt.

The integrated video is the best and easier way to conserve the power. But at the same time it is the lowest performance. For the office users, casual browsing and pure 2D use the integrated video is the best one while comparing with the discrete video.

E) Display:

Cold cathode fluorescent is been used for the LCD monitors to provide light for the display.

F) Material recycling:

Recycling means reusing electronic waste or any other products. When the recycle process is done with the computer equipment another system can be found. Recycling computing equipment can keep harmful materials such as lead, mercury, and hexavalent chromium out of landfills.

G) Telecommuting:

In green computing teleconferencing and telepresence are implemented. The advantages of telecommuting are increase in the work station, reduction of greenhouse gas emission.

CHEMICAL USED:

There are many chemical elements used in the green computing. They are lead, mercury and cadmium. Some of the elements are found in large amount and they are tin, lead, silicon, carbon, iron and aluminium. The elements which are found in less number are cadmium and mercury. The problems caused when using these elements are listed below:

- **Lead :**

It is been used in soldering of printed circuit board and other components. It is also been used in the glass for CRT. In the year 1997, the scientists found that 1.2 billion tons of lead were used in the computer components. When we are using this much amount of lead it causes some problem. The problems which are created by using lead are been listed below:

- It causes damage to the human body by affecting the nervous system, blood system, kidney and it cause negative effects on child brain development.
- It accumulates in the environment and has toxic effects on plants, animals and microorganisms.
- Electronics contribute 40% of the total amount of lead found in landfills and can make its way from landfills into the water supplies.

- **Mercury:**

It is been used in the batteries, switches, housing, printed circuit boards. It is been found in the medical, data transmission, telecommunication and as well as in the cell phones. The problem caused by using mercury is it spreads out in water transforming into methylated mercury which easily accumulates in living organisms. Mercury spreads out in water transforming into methylated mercury which easily accumulates in living organisms.

When we use methylated mercury it can cause chronic brain damage.

- **Cadmium:**

It is been used in resistors for chips, infrared detectors and in semiconductors. It is been found that the 2 million pound of mercury is been used in the computer components in the

year 1997 and 2004. The problem caused while using the cadmium it is absorbed through respiration and also food intake. Cadmium has a half life of 30 years so that cadmium can poison a human body slowly through the human's life.

PLASTIC:

Plastic is been used in the computer. They found that 4 billion pounds were used for building the computer and components purpose between the year 1997 and 2004. One kind of plastic is been used for cablings and housing. That type of plastic is known as polyvinyl chloride. This type of plastic is very difficult for recycling and if we burn this of plastic it produces dioxins and furans. The plastic which are used in the computer are mostly treated with the flame retardant chemicals which can cause cancer for the human begins. So the best way is the plastic product which cannot be recycled can be avoided.

THE SOLUTION TO REDUCE THE CHEMICAL PROBLEMS:

The best solution is recycling. The computer components can be donated to the people who do not have or those who in lesser amount. This is however leads to the older computers being dumped but there is probably no way around this as eventually the older computers would be discarded anyway. When the recycling process is used the companies for plastic and other components it reduces the waste and toxins. In Europe, the plastics are discarded instead of recycled because the flame retardant chemicals are too toxic to work with.

EXAMPLE:

The example for the green computing is thin client. A Thin Client is a computer or a computer program which depends heavily on some other computer to full fill its traditional computational roles. It is like a regular computer. It does not have hard drives. Thin client can run the server with the help of the software. It is been connected to the server through the networks.

GOALS:

Green computing goals are somewhat related to the green chemistry which is to reduce the use of hazardous materials, maximize energy efficiency during the product's lifetime and promote the recyclability or biodegradability of defunct product and factory waste.

Research continues into key areas such as making the use of computers as energy-efficient as possible, and designing algorithms and systems for efficiency-related computer technologies.

ASPECT OF GREEN COMPUTING:

The aspects are been followed to be green and they are listed below:

- The green use is been used for minimizing the electricity consumption.
- Green disposal is been followed for re-making the unwanted electronic equipments.
- Green design is been used for the designing purpose of some digital device.
- Green manufacturing is been used for the reduction in the manufacturing and some other subsystems.

RECENT IMPLEMENTATION:

New implementation has been taken place in the green computing.

- Blackleg.
- Zebu computing.
- Sunray thin computing.

- The Asus Eee PC and other ultra portables.

Blackleg:

Blackleg is a search-engine site powered by Google Search. This concept was based on the computer, when it displays white screen presenting a word or google home. 59w is consumed when the screen is black. This type of implementation is done for displaying the different color for consuming the energy. Each color consume different amount of energy in the monitor.

Zebu computing:

It is an energy efficient pc. It consumes one-third of the power of a light bulb. 1.2 gigahertz processor and 512 meg of RAM runs an LINUX operating system.

Sunray thin computing:

Customer interest in the sunray has been increased due to the sun microsystems reporting. A thin client as electricity prices climb. It generates less electricity than conventional desktop. The heavy computation is been performed by the server, so the sunray produce 4 to 8 watt of power in the desktop. Thin client does not have more powerful processor and hard drives but the PCS have it.

The Asus Eee PC and other ultra portable:

The "ultra-portable" class of personal computers is characterized by a small size, fairly low power CPU, compact screen, low cost and innovations such as using flash memory for storage rather than hard drives with spinning platters. The example of Asus Eee PC is ultra portable. It is the size of a paperback, weighs less than a kilogram, has built-in Wi-Fi and uses flash memory instead of a hard drive. It runs LINUX operating system.

WAYS FOR IMPLEMENTING:

- Reversible computer can be used for the less power consumption.
- Toxic material like lead is been used so it can be replaced by copper and silver.
- Use a lower power desktop or laptop while using high power.
- When the processing is done by the server, thin client use only 4 to 8 watt power.
- If we use pc, buy a lower power desktop which saves power consumption and cooling requirement.
- Usage of the data centre power should be measured.
- Replacing the CRT screen by LCD screen.
- Avoid unwanted upgrades of the operating system and hardware drives.
- When the pc or laptop is not in use the switch off it.
- Buy the hardware from the manufacturing companies which have recycling process of hardware.
- Do not send the computer equipments to the landfills, instead of that it can be recycled.
- Electronic hardware products should also be strictly adhering to the restricted use of hazardous substances.
- Lead-tin solder in use today is very malleable making it an ideal shock absorber.

MERITS AND DEMERITS:

- During the peak operation energy consumption is been reduced.
- During some operations it saves more energy.
- The best idea is to use eco-friendly sources of energy.
- The computer wastes can be reduced.

- Harmful effects of the computing resources can be reduced.

CONCLUSION:

If the green computing is been implemented in the business field the cost of the paper and power consumption can be reduced. New green computing is done by replacing the toxic materials. Year by year new implementation are added to the green computing. When people buy computers they only care about the cost and speed they do not worry about the ecology impact. So the green computing must be spread to all around the world to make our environment green. Everyone should put their own effort for it. Some the efforts can be followed by every people are

- Don't print the copies of the email until it is necessary for you.
- Whenever you take print out try to use the paper which is used one side.
- Try to buy the printer which can print on both sides.
- Turn off the whole computer when it is not in use. It may saves energy.
- Note that the paper which is been used for printing can be recycled.
- If you need to print then turn on the printing machine.

If everyone put some efforts shortly our environment cab been turned to green.

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